

Fluorescent Supramolecular Gels based on D-Sorbitol Derivatives

Emmanuel Odella, Miryam Criado-Gonzalez, Rodrigo A. Ponzio, David Mecerreyes, Matías L. Picchio and Daniele Mantione**

E. Odella, R. A. Ponzio.

Instituto de Investigaciones en Tecnologías Energéticas y Materiales Avanzados (IITEMA), Universidad Nacional de Río Cuarto (UNRC), Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Tecnológicas (CONICET). Río Cuarto X5804BYA, Córdoba, Argentina.

M. Criado-Gonzalez.

Institute of Polymer Science and Technology (ICTP-CSIC). Juan de la Cierva 3, 28006 Madrid, Spain.

M. L. Picchio.

POLYMAT, Department of Mining-Metallurgy Engineering and Materials Science, School of Engineering, University of the Basque Country (UPV/ EHU). Plaza Torres Quevedo 1, 48013 Bilbao, Spain.

M. L. Picchio, D. Mantione, D. Mecerreyes.

IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science. Plaza Euskadi 5, 48009 Bilbao, Spain.

matiasluis.picchiop@ehu.es, daniele.mantione@ehu.es.

D. Mantione, D. Mecerreyes.

POLYMAT, University of the Basque Country UPV/EHU. Avenida Tolosa 72, 20018 Donostia-San Sebastián, Spain.

Funding: M.L.P. gratefully acknowledges the financial support from the Basque Government, Department of Education (IT1766-22). D.M., D.M., and M.L.P. acknowledge the financial support from IKERBASQUE - Basque Foundation for Science. This research was funded by the European Union under the IONBIKE 2.0 project (grant agreement n. 101129945, <https://doi.org/10.3030/101129945>).

Keywords: fluorescent low-molecular-weight gelators, d-sorbitol, ambidextrous, eutectogels, deep eutectic solvents.

Abstract. Supramolecular gels formed by low-molecular-weight gelators (LMWGs) are valuable soft materials due to their remarkable versatility and wide range of applications. Developing ambidextrous LMWGs that self-assemble in diverse solvents remains challenging, as such versatility requires precise molecular engineering to ensure robust structuring across varying polarity and hydrogen-bonding environments. Here, we present a family of sugar-based molecules functionalized with naphthyl (DNapS), benzothiadiazole (DBTDS), and coumarin (MCumS) moieties, synthesized by a green, scalable method, which serve as fluorescent LMWGs. Their gelation abilities are evaluated in water, organic solvents of different polarities, and deep eutectic solvents (DES). Among them, MCumS forms gels in water, short-chain alcohols, and terpene-based hydrophobic DES, highlighting its potential as a rare example of an LMWG capable of gelation across chemically diverse environments. Morphological analysis of MCumS gels reveals fibrous network formation in water and distinct, solvent-dependent architectures in eutectogels. Interestingly, supramolecular gels based on this LMWG and zwitterionic DES show superior viscoelastic behavior and injectability. These findings not only expand the library of fluorescent LMWGs but also contribute to the fundamental understanding of structure-property relationships in versatile supramolecular gel systems.

1. Introduction

Supramolecular gels, a class of soft materials formed by the self-assembly of low-molecular weight-gelators (LMWGs), are integrated into numerous high-tech materials in fields covering drug delivery, tissue engineering, catalysis, environmental remediation, molecular sensing, and nanoelectronics.^[1-4] These systems arise from the organization of small molecules into three-dimensional networks through noncovalent interactions, typically triggered by external stimuli.^[1,5-7] Among the various LMWGs reported to date, 1,3:2,4-Dibenzylidene-D-sorbitol (DBS) remains one of the most efficient and widely used gelators.^[8-11] DBS can self-assemble and form gels in numerous organic solvents,^[12] monomers,^[13] polymer melts,^[10] liquid crystals,^[14] ionic liquids,^[8] and deep eutectic solvents (DES).^[9,15] However, its practical applicability is limited by its pronounced hydrophobicity, which prevents stable gel formation in water unless additional functional groups, such as carboxylic acid^[16] or hydrazides^[17] are introduced.

Beyond solvent compatibility, another important limitation of DBS and most of its substituted analogs is the lack of intrinsic fluorescence. Fluorescent LMWGs have attracted considerable interest in supramolecular materials research, as intrinsic emission provides an additional handle to probe self-assembly processes and expand the functional scope of gel systems.^[18-21] Although several fluorescent LMWGs have been reported,^[18,22,23] their rational design remains challenging. In many cases, fluorescence is introduced through the covalent attachment of external fluorophores, typically requiring multistep synthetic routes, expensive reagents or catalysts, and extensive purification steps. These synthetic and economic constraints severely limit scalability, reproducibility, and the practical integration of fluorescent LMWGs into functional materials and devices.

In this context, there is a clear need for simple, scalable, and rational molecular design strategies that enable the development of intrinsically fluorescent LMWGs while preserving broad solvent versatility and efficient gelation. Guided by the hypothesis that an aromatic fluorophore can simultaneously promote self-assembly and provide fluorescence features, we report here a family of fluorescent LMWGs derived from the commercially available D-sorbitol. Using a straightforward one-step condensation reaction with readily accessible fluorescent aldehydes, three intrinsically fluorescent LMWGs functionalized with naphthyl (DNapS), benzothiadiazole (DBTDS), and coumarin (MCumS) moieties were synthesized (Scheme 1a). The selected aromatic units combine π -conjugation, structural rigidity, and well-established photophysical properties, which are expected to enhance π - π interactions during self-assembly while acting as sensitive fluorophores.

Importantly, by preserving the D-sorbitol core and varying only the aromatic aldehyde, a rational molecular design is achieved in which the hydrophilic-hydrophobic balance can be modified. This approach enables the proper evaluation of structure-property relationships and ensures favorable conditions for self-assembly and gel formation. To the best of our knowledge, only a limited number of fluorescent D-sorbitol-based LMWGs have been reported, and these systems typically exhibit gelation restricted to a narrow range of solvent systems, including chlorinated aromatics, binary polar mixtures, fatty alcohols, or oils.^[24–26] Moreover, these D-sorbitol-based LMWGs require either more than one-step synthesis^[27] or the incorporation of an external fluorophore.^[28,29]

In this work, the three fluorescent LMWGs were thoroughly characterized, and their gelation ability was systematically evaluated in water, organic solvents of different polarities, and deep eutectic solvents (DES). Particular attention was devoted to DES-based systems, which have recently emerged as sustainable and highly tunable media for supramolecular gels with promising future applications.^[30,31] Notably, among the investigated gelators, MCumS was identified as the only compound capable of forming stable gels both in water and in a DES environment. Given the rarity of LMWGs that combine intrinsic fluorescence with stable eutectogel formation, a comprehensive and detailed investigation of the MCumS/Thymol:Menthol and MCumS/Thymol:Betaine systems was carried out.

Overall, this study introduces a minimalist yet versatile molecular design strategy for the development of intrinsically fluorescent LMWGs, enabling the formation of gels across diverse solvent environments, opening new avenues for their application in sustainable and advanced soft materials.

2. Results and Discussions

2.1. Synthesis and Characterization of LMWGs

The LMWGs were designed and synthesized following well-known procedures (see supporting information (SI) section).^[32,33] D-sorbitol was used as a common precursor, while benzo[c][1,2,5]thiadiazole-4-carbaldehyde (BTD-CHO), 2-Naphthaldehyde (Nap-CHO), and 2-Oxo-2H-chromene-6-carbaldehyde (Cum-CHO) were chosen as the aldehyde source for the acetal formation (Scheme 1a). The acid-catalyzed reaction between BTD-CHO and Nap-CHO with D-sorbitol led to the diacetal molecules DBTDS and DNapS, respectively, while the monoacetal derivative MCumS was only isolated in a good yield between D-sorbitol and Cum-CHO. The distinct acetalization behavior observed for the different aldehydes can be rationalized based on their electronic and structural features. In the case of MCumS,

conjugation of the aldehyde group with the coumarin moiety (bearing an α,β -unsaturated lactone) promotes delocalization of the positive charge in the protonated carbonyl intermediate, thereby reducing the electrophilicity of the aldehyde. Under the mild acidic conditions employed, this electronic effect favors formation of a stabilized mono-acetal species.^[8,33] Furthermore, the rigidity of the coumarin moiety results in a conformationally constrained mono-acetal, which limits the accessibility and reactivity of the remaining hydroxyl groups of sorbitol. As a consequence, further acetalization becomes kinetically disfavored.

In contrast, the naphthyl (Nap-CHO) and benzothiadiazole (BTD-CHO) aldehydes exhibit higher electrophilicity and do not provide comparable stabilization of the initially formed acetal. The reversible character of the acetalization process therefore enables subsequent condensation, leading to the formation of di-acetal products under identical reaction conditions. Additionally, the Nap-CHO and BTD-CHO units appear to impose fewer geometric constraints, allowing sufficient conformational flexibility for reorganization of the sorbitol backbone and formation of a second acetal ring. In the cases of DNapS and DBTDS, precipitation of the poorly soluble di-acetals from methanol may further shift the equilibrium toward double acetalization, reinforcing the preferential formation of the bis-substituted products. ¹H NMR analysis confirmed the cyclic acetal formation in all cases (**Figure 1a** and Figure S1-S6).

Scheme 1. (a) One-step synthetic preparation of fluorescent D-sorbitol-based LMWGs derivatives. The LMWGs are color-coded as: DNapS (red), DBTDS (green), and MCumS (blue), and this colour code is used consistently throughout the figures for clarity. (b)

Ambidextrous nature of MCumS enabling the formation of hydrogels, organogels, and eutectogels.

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy was also employed to characterize the LMWGs (Figure 1b). For all the compounds, the characteristic peaks of the cyclic acetal structure ($\nu\text{O-C-O}$) are situated at ≈ 1177 , 1094 , and 1022 cm^{-1} ,^[34] while the broad band observed in the $3220\text{-}3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range corresponds to the OH stretching vibrational mode (νOH). In the case of both DNapS and MCumS, the νOH is broad and located at $\approx 3270\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\approx 3325\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively, indicating the dominance of intermolecular hydrogen bond interactions in both compounds. On the contrary, for DBTDS, the νOH is located at a considerably higher frequency ($\approx 3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$). The molecular structure of DBTDS suggests the potential formation of a bifurcated intramolecular hydrogen-bonding system involving the 5-OH group, the acetal oxygen, and the benzothiadiazole nitrogen. This structural configuration could provide a rational explanation for the observed higher frequency.^[35] This peculiar three-atom-centered interaction could also explain the different chemical shifts observed in DBTDS for the methine hydrogens of each cyclic acetal connecting the benzothiadiazole moieties (Figure 1a). Each gelator also exhibits distinct characteristic peaks. For MCumS, the carbonyl stretching vibration ($\nu\text{C=O}$) of the coumarin moiety appears at approximately 1690 cm^{-1} .^[36] For the DBTDS, the C=N stretching vibration ($\nu\text{C=N}$) of the benzothiadiazole core is located at 1554 cm^{-1} , while the peaks of the characteristic S-N stretching ($\nu\text{C=N}$) and C-H out-of-plane bending ($\gamma\text{C-H}$) modes are shown at $\approx 860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\approx 755\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively.^[37]

Figure 1. (a) ^1H NMR spectra of DNapS (red line) and MCumS (blue line) in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$, and DBTDS (green line) in CDCl_3 . Signals of the methine protons forming the cyclic acetal are indicated by a solid circle in the molecular structures of the LMWGs (right). (b) ATR-FTIR spectra of solid DNapS (red line), MCumS (blue line), and DBTDS (green line) LMWGs. Characteristic vibrational modes are shown in the Figure. The shaded areas at 3100-3500 cm^{-1} and 1000-1250 cm^{-1} represent the frequency regions in which the OH stretching and 1,3-dioxalene ring vibrational modes are observed, respectively.

2.2. Initial gel screening

The gelation capacity of the three LMWGs was evaluated across a range of solvents, including water, organic solvents of different polarities, and DES of different natures (**Table**

1). Four DES were used for testing the formation of eutectogels: Urea:Choline chloride (U:ChCl, 2:1 molar ratio), Glycerol:Choline chloride (Gly:ChCl, 2:1 molar ratio), Thymol:Menthol (Thy:Men, 1:2 molar ratio), and Thymol:Betaine (Thy:Bet, 4:1 molar ratio). The supramolecular gels were formed by heating the suspension of the LMWGs in each solvent until a temperature close to the boiling point of the solvent, and then left to cool down to room temperature.

Table 1. DNapS, MCumS, and DBTDS gelation tests in water and organic solvents (1% w/v) and in DES (3% w/v) upon the heating-cooling cycle. G: gel, I: insoluble, S: soluble, P: precipitate, T: translucent, O: opaque.

Solvent / Solvent Mixtures	DNapS	MCumS	DBTDS
Toluene	G (O)	I	G (T)
1,4 Dioxane	G (T)	I	S
EtOAc	I	I	G (O)
CHCl ₃	I	I	P
Acetone	I	I	S
DMF	S	S	S
DMSO	S	S	S
ACN	I	I	P
Hexanol	I	G (T)	I
Butanol	I	G (T)	I
EtOH	I	I	G (T)
DMSO:Water (50% v/v)	I	G (T)	I
U:ChCl	G (O)	I	G (O)
Gly:ChCl	I	I	I

Thy:Men	G (O)	G (O)	G (O)
Thy:Bet	G (O)	G (O)	G (O)
Water		G (O)	

The LMWGs DBTDS and DNapS showed good gelation capacity in aromatic solvents such as toluene. DBTDS also displayed good gelation behavior in EtOH and EtOAc. Neither DBTDS nor DNapS was able to form gels in water, as they remained insoluble at the concentrations tested. MCumS was practically insoluble in all the non-polar organic solvents evaluated, although polar solvents with good hydrogen bond capabilities, such as DMSO, tended to solubilize it. However, after a heating-cooling cycle, the mixture remained fully soluble, with no evidence of gel formation. Interestingly, the mono-acetal MCumS is not soluble in EtOH but showed gelation properties in alcohols with larger carbon tails such as *n*-butanol and *n*-hexanol. More remarkably, MCumS was the only gelator capable of forming gel in water among the synthesized molecules, thus highlighting its ambidextrous character (Scheme 1b).

2.3. Gelation in Conventional Solvents

Although the three LMWGs display a limited gelation ability and form gels only in a restricted number of solvents, this behavior is not uncommon in supramolecular gel systems and reflects the delicate balance of non-covalent interactions governing self-assembly. In this context, for each LMWGs, we selected a representative gel formed in a solvent where a stable and reproducible gelation was observed. This approach allows a meaningful investigation of the self-assembly features intrinsic to each LMWG under favorable conditions, while avoiding ambiguities associated with poorly defined or metastable systems. Importantly, the selected representative gels are not intended to imply general gelation behavior across all solvents, but rather to serve as model systems that capture the characteristic aggregation mode and structural organization of each LMWG. Therefore, the DNapS/toluene, DBTDS/EtOAc, and MCumS/water systems were selected for detailed analysis.

The fluorescence properties of these representative gels are shown in **Figure 2a-c**. Upon gelation in toluene, DNapS shows a distinct evolution of its emission properties compared to the molecularly dissolved state (Figure 2a). In solution, the emission is dominated by the structured naphthalene monomeric form (non-aggregated) with fluorescence emission maximum (λ_{max}) at 333 nm and shoulders at 326 nm and 350 nm, consistent with the typical photophysics of naphthalene-containing gelators.^[38-41] Gel formation induces two new emissive features as consequence of the enhancement of π - π stacking interactions: a red-shifted

band with λ_{max} at 364 nm, attributed to monomer emission in a more rigid environment,^[38] and a band centered at ≈ 415 nm, arising from closely packed naphthyl moieties within the gel network, consistent with observations in numerous LMWGs bearing pendant naphthyl groups.^[38–41] In the case of DBTDS, the gelator exhibited a λ_{max} at 385 nm in EtOAc solution, which underwent a bathochromic shift to 402 nm after forming the organogel, also suggesting enhanced π - π stacking interactions in the gel state (Figure 2b).^[25] Similar findings were observed for MCumS/water hydrogels, which showed a shift from 388 nm in solution to 401 nm in the gel state (Figure 2c).

Figure 2. Spectroscopic characterization of DNapS (left), DBTDS (central), and MCumS (right) gels. Normalized fluorescence spectra of LMWGs in both solution and gel states: (a) DNapS/toluene ($\lambda_{\text{exc}}=300$ nm), (b) DBTDS/EtOAc ($\lambda_{\text{exc}}=311$ nm), and (c) MCumS/water ($\lambda_{\text{exc}}=310$ nm). Pictures of the gels under UV light ($\lambda=365$ nm) are shown in the inset. ATR-FTIR spectra of: (d) DNapS powder and the resulting xerogel formed in toluene. (e) DBTDS powder and the resulting xerogel formed in EtOAc. (f) MCumS powder and the resulting cryogel formed in water.

The aggregation-induced changes observed in the fluorescence spectra prompted us to investigate the nature of the intermolecular interactions stabilizing the assembled state. Figures 2d-f compare the ATR-FTIR spectra of the three LMWGs in their solid state and dry gels.

Different characteristic vibrational modes are affected by the gelation process. In the case of DNaPS in toluene (Figure 2d), the νOH located at $\approx 3270\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to $\approx 3220\text{ cm}^{-1}$, suggesting that the intermolecular hydrogen bonding increased upon self-assembly and gelation. For DBTDS in EtOAc (Figure 2e), a notable shift from $\nu\text{OH} \approx 3450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ to $\nu\text{OH} \approx 3225\text{ cm}^{-1}$ was also observed. This suggests that the solvent disrupts the strong intramolecular hydrogen bond present in DBTDS, thereby facilitating the formation of an intermolecular hydrogen-bonded network during the self-assembly process. The same trend, although to a lesser extent, was observable for the cryogel formed by MCumS (Figure 2f). The νOH slightly shifted from $\approx 3325\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the solid state to $\approx 3310\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the cryogel, which also suggests an increase in the hydrogen bonding upon gel formation. There is no notable shift in the $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$, which could indicate that the coumarin moiety is not involved in hydrogen bonding interactions.

The presence of both hydrogen-bonding and π - π stacking interactions suggested the formation of extended supramolecular architectures, which were subsequently investigated in their native gel state by Small Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS).^[42-44] **Figures 3a-c** show the X-ray scattering profiles of DNaPS/toluene, DBTDS/EtOAc, and MCumS/water gels, respectively. All three systems were fitted by a combination of a flexible cylinder (or flexible elliptical cylinder) and a power law model (see SI for further details), aiming to capture the anisotropic and semi-flexible nature of the supramolecular assemblies formed by the gelators and to account for network heterogeneity, respectively.^[42,43] This choice is consistent with the well-known tendency of LMWGs based on D-sorbitol to form elongated, one-dimensional aggregates driven by directional noncovalent interactions such as π - π stacking and hydrogen-bonding.^[8] Moreover, such combined models have been successfully applied to describe the structure of other low-molecular-weight gel systems.^[42,45,46] The resulting fitting parameters are summarized in Table S1.

Figure 3. Structural and morphological characterization of DNapS (left), DBTDS (central), and MCumS (right) gels. SAXS profiles for (a) DNapS/toluene, (b) DBTDS/EtOAc, and (c) MCumS/water gels. The experimental data are shown as filled circles, and the model fits as solid lines. SEM images of (d) DNapS/toluene xerogel, (e) DBTDS/EtOAc xerogel, and (f) MCumS/water cryogel. Pictures of the gels under natural light are shown in the inset. The scale bar in all SEM images is 5 μm . XRD diffraction patterns of (g) DNapS/toluene, (h) DBTDS/EtOAc, and (i) MCumS/water xerogels.

SAXS data of the DNapS/toluene organogel were successfully modeled using a combined flexible cylinder and power law approach (Figure 3a). The flexible cylinder component yielded a fibril radius of approximately 3.7 nm and a Kuhn length of ≈ 12 nm, consistent with semi-flexible supramolecular fibers stabilized by π - π stacking of the naphthyl groups and hydrogen bonding within the hydroxyl groups. These dimensions are typical of LMWGs systems and represent the primary building blocks of the gel network.^[42,47] The additional power law contribution, with an exponent close to 3, indicates the presence of sheet-like aggregates,

dominating the scattering at low q . This suggests a multilevel assembly process in which primary fibrils further associate into dense bundles and extended domains. In the case of DBTDS/EtOAc organogel, the scattering profile was described using a combined flexible elliptical cylinder and power law model, revealing the anisotropy in the cross-section of the supramolecular fibers (Figure 3b). The extracted dimensions suggest ribbon-like fibrils with an elliptical cross-section and a major-to-minor axis ratio exceeding 3, consistent with lamellar or tape-like assemblies. The relatively short Kuhn length (≈ 6 nm) implies enhanced flexibility, thus favoring fiber entanglement and network formation. The power law contribution exhibits an exponent greater than 4, indicative of sharp interfaces and compact higher-order aggregates, consistent with lamellar stacking and dense fibril bundling.^[43] SAXS analysis of MCumS/water hydrogel was also described using a combined flexible elliptical cylinder and power law model, revealing the formation of long, semi-rigid supramolecular fibrils with an anisotropic cross-section (Figure 3c). The resulting fitted parameters suggest the existence of primary fibers with nanometric cross-sections. Moreover, the Kuhn length (≈ 17 nm) also reflects semi-flexible fibers, likely arising from cooperative π - π stacking of coumarin units and extensive hydrogen bonding involving the free hydroxyl groups of the LMWGs. The power law contribution, with an exponent close to 3, is indicative of a mass-fractal, highly porous network lacking sharp interfaces, characteristic of hydrated gel systems.^[43]

SAXS analysis provided evidence for fibrillar aggregates with nanometric cross-sections. To visualize the resulting network morphology at the micrometer scale, SEM analysis of the corresponding xerogels was performed. DNapS/toluene xerogel displayed sharp, needle-like crystals emerging from larger sheet-like structures (Figure 3d). These well-defined domains suggest anisotropic molecular organization, likely driven by π - π stacking or hydrophobic interactions with toluene. Dense, interconnected fibrils (≈ 0.5 μm cross-section) were also visible, with gaps and voids indicating micro and mesoporosity. This is consistent with the multilevel hierarchical organization inferred from SAXS, where primary supramolecular fibers associate into dense, anisotropic bundles and extended sheet-like domains. In contrast, the DBTDS/EtOAc xerogel exhibited a highly porous, interwoven nanofibrous network (Figure 3e). The fibers formed randomly ordered, entangled assemblies with lamellar-like structures averaging 0.5-1 μm . These observations are in agreement with the SAXS-derived model of flexible, anisotropic ribbon-like fibrils and compact higher-order aggregates. Figure 3f shows the cryogel from MCumS in water. SEM revealed a porous nanofibrillar network composed of long fibers (≈ 150 nm diameter, micrometers long) forming interconnected structures. These nanofibrils entangle into thicker filaments (~ 1.1 μm cross-section). Their fine and uniform

nature suggests self-assembly driven by directional non-covalent interactions, including π - π stacking between coumarin moieties and hydrogen bonding by hydroxyl groups. The observed morphology is consistent with the structural model proposed by the SAXS analysis, consisting of semi-flexible, anisotropic supramolecular fibrils. Across all gel systems, the larger apparent fiber dimensions observed by SEM can be attributed to the fibril bundling and partial collapse or aggregation during the drying process, whereas SAXS selectively probes the primary hydrated fibrils in the native gel state.^[44,48]

While SEM reveals the overall morphology of the dried supramolecular networks, X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were carried out to gain insight into the molecular packing within the supramolecular assemblies. Figures 3g-i show the XRD studies of DNapS/toluene, DBTDS/EtOAc, and MCumS/water xerogels, respectively. The XRD pattern of DNapS/toluene xerogel (Figure 3g) is characterized by a strong low-angle diffraction peak at $2\theta=4.54^\circ$ ($d=19.42 \text{ \AA}$), followed by additional diffraction peaks at $2\theta=9.57^\circ$ ($d=9.23 \text{ \AA}$) and $2\theta=13.29^\circ$ ($d=6.66 \text{ \AA}$). The corresponding d-spacings exhibit an approximate 1:1/2:1/3 reciprocal ratio, which is indicative of an internal lamellar organization within the fibrillar assemblies, reflecting efficient molecular packing and accounting for the formation of compact fibrils as observed by SEM (Figure 3d). Moreover, the peak at the region of $2\theta=22.4-23.9^\circ$ ($d=3.9-3.7 \text{ \AA}$) suggests an important contribution of π - π stacking interactions between naphthyl groups in DNapS gelator.^[33,38] For the case of DBTDS/EtOAc xerogel (Figure 3h), the main distinguishable diffraction peaks are centered at $2\theta=5.00^\circ$ ($d=17.65 \text{ \AA}$), 8.60° ($d=10.27 \text{ \AA}$), and 10.25° ($d=8.62 \text{ \AA}$). The broad nature of these diffractions indicates limited long-range periodicity, consistent with a weakly semicrystalline fibrillar organization arising from one-dimensional self-assembly. The structural features derived from XRD show good correlation with the mesoscale organization observed by SEM (Figure 3e). Finally, the XRD pattern of MCumS/water xerogel (Figure 3i) exhibits characteristic diffraction peaks at $2\theta=6.09^\circ$ ($d=14.5 \text{ \AA}$), 10.43° ($d=8.5 \text{ \AA}$), 12.47° ($d=7.1 \text{ \AA}$), 17.45° ($d=5.1 \text{ \AA}$), and 20.97° ($d=4.2 \text{ \AA}$), indicating the presence of supramolecular order within the material. The intense peaks at 6.09° , 12.47° , and 17.45° display an approximate 1:1/2:1/3 d-spacing relationship, consistent with a lamellar organization with an interlayer distance of 14.5 \AA . The additional diffraction peaks in the $10-13^\circ$ range suggest internal ordering associated with intermolecular packing and short-range correlations. Therefore, the diffraction features support a one-dimensional supramolecular assembly with well-defined local order, in accordance with the fibrillar morphology observed by SEM (Figure 3f) and by other gelators based on monoacetal of D-sorbitol.^[26,33,49] This structural interpretation is further supported by circular dichroism measurements (Figure S7), which

provide complementary evidence of supramolecular chiral organization under gel-forming conditions.

We also investigated the viscoelastic behavior of DNapS/toluene and DBTDS/EtOAc organogels by large amplitude oscillatory shear (Figure S8a-f). Unfortunately, the MCumS/water hydrogel was too fragile and did not exhibit clear solid-like viscoelastic behavior, with the dynamic moduli overlapping across the entire amplitude and frequency ranges studied (Figure S9a,b). Results in Figure S8a-d show that both organogels present a similar linear viscoelastic range (lower than $\approx 10\%$) and elastic modulus (G') in the order of 10^4 Pa. Interestingly, dynamic step-strain tests revealed that DBTDS/EtOAc organogels display self-healing behavior, with fast thixotropic recovery (Figure S8f). In contrast, DNapS/toluene showed only partial recovery, with G' one order of magnitude lower than its original ($\approx 10^3$ Pa). The lack of full viscoelastic recovery observed for the DNapS/toluene organogels can be attributed to the formation of rigid, highly packed fibrillar and lamellar domains, which hinder network rearrangement after large deformations and limit the reversibility of supramolecular interactions.

2.4. Gelation in Deep Eutectic Solvents

As shown in Table 1, all three synthesized LMWGs exhibited gelation capacity in non-conventional media such as DES. Remarkably, the successful gelation in terpene-based DES (Thy:Men and Thy:Bet) appears to be independent of the molecular structure of the LMWGs, as all of them were able to form eutectogels in these mixtures. However, as only MCumS was capable to gelate water and selected alcohols, we focused subsequent studies on its gelation behavior in these specific DES mixtures, chosen for their well-documented hydrogen-bonding ability and hydrophobic nature.^[50]

The emissive properties of MCumS in these media were verified. As a representative example, the fluorescence emission spectra of MCumS/Thy:Bet showed no appreciable change in λ_{\max} (540 nm) upon gel formation (Figure S10). **Figures 4a,b** show the ATR-FTIR spectra of MCumS/Thy:Men and MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogels, respectively. In MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel, the main peaks of the gelator showed no significant shifts after gelation, though the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ intensity moderately decreased. This suggests that the coumarin moiety is affected during gelation, likely through π - π stacking promoted by the hydrophobic Thy:Men DES, which alters the carbonyl electron density. In MCumS/Thy:Bet, the ν_{OH} band shifted from ≈ 3325 to ≈ 3290 cm^{-1} , indicating stronger polar and hydrogen-bonding interactions from the zwitterionic Bet.

As in Thy:Men, the $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ band remained unshifted but showed reduced intensity, implying that the coumarin group participates in noncovalent interactions during eutectogel formation.

Figure 4. Spectroscopic and morphological characterization of MCumS/Thy:Men (left) and MCumS/Thy:Bet (right) eutectogels. ATR-FTIR spectra of (a) MCumS/Thy:Men and (b) MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogels. The spectra of MCumS powder and pure DES are included for comparison. SEM images of (c) MCumS/Thy:Men and (d) MCumS/Thy:Bet xerogels. The scale bar is 5 μm . Picture of the eutectogels under natural light are shown in the inset.

The influence of the DES media on the microstructure of eutectogels formed by MCumS was also investigated by SEM. The eutectogel derived from the non-ionic Thy:Men DES displayed a textured and porous morphology, characterized by interconnected lamellae and thin sheet-like structures (Figure 4c). These features suggest a gel network formed *via* extended supramolecular self-assembly, likely driven by π - π stacking interactions among the coumarin rings of MCumS and hydrophobic forces mediated by the low-polarity DES environment. The eutectogel formed in the zwitterionic Thy:Bet DES displayed a dense and amorphous matrix with smooth surfaces and minimal porosity (Figure 4d). No distinct fibrous or lamellar domains

were seen, suggesting amorphous solidification and limited long-range order in the gel network. The MCumS gelator may remain partially solvated or constrained by strong interactions with Bet, hindering fiber or lamella formation during the gelation process.

Complementary SAXS and XRD studies were also performed for MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel. For SAXS analysis (Figure S11), the parameters extracted from the combined flexible elliptical cylinder and power law model (Table S1) indicate flattened objects and large persistence lengths, consistent with rigid lamellar structures extending beyond the accessible SAXS length scale, as observed in SEM (Figure 4c). The power law contribution, with an exponent of approximately 2.7, reflects a mass-fractal lamellar network with long-range heterogeneity.^[43] The X-ray diffraction pattern of the MCumS/Thy:Men xerogel (Figure S12) displays an intense diffraction peak at $2\theta=8.32^\circ$ ($d=10.6 \text{ \AA}$), a weak diffraction peak at 12.42° ($d=7.1 \text{ \AA}$), and a broad feature centered at $\approx 16.7^\circ$ ($d=5.3 \text{ \AA}$). The first peak ($2\theta=8.32^\circ$), corresponds to a characteristic spacing of approximately 1.0-1.1 nm and is attributed to the supramolecular organization of the gelator aggregates responsible for network formation. The second diffuse maximum at $\approx 16.7^\circ$ reflects short-range lateral packing within the aggregates and indicates local order without extended crystallinity. It should be noted that complete removal of the Thy:Men DES is challenging; therefore, the residual solvent may contribute to the broad diffraction feature observed at $2\theta \approx 16.7^\circ$, leading to an overlap between the amorphous scattering of the DES and the short-range packing of the gelator, as seen in analogous systems formed in DES-based environments.^[9,51] Overall, the diffraction features reveal a hierarchically organized yet non-crystalline structure, as seen in other eutectogels where gelation is governed by short-range supramolecular interactions.^[9,51,52] The XRD features are consistent with an extended supramolecular assembly and correlate with the lamellar and sheet-like architectures observed by SEM (Figure 4c).

We investigated the viscoelastic behavior of MCumS-based eutectogels to assess their structural and functional properties. Strain sweep tests showed that MCumS/Thy:Bet (**Figure 5a**) maintained integrity up to $\approx 1\%$ strain and yielded at $\approx 8\%$, exhibiting high stiffness (high G'). In contrast, MCumS/Thy:Men (Figure 5d) had much lower G' but tolerated higher deformation (yield at $\approx 45\%$), showing greater stretchability. Frequency sweeps confirmed solid-like behavior ($G' > G''$) for both eutectogels, but MCumS/Thy:Bet showed a much higher G' (Figure 5b, $\approx 7000 \text{ Pa}$) than MCumS/Thy:Men (Figure 5e, $\approx 400 \text{ Pa}$), reflecting a stronger and more elastic network. These differences likely stem from the distinct physicochemical properties of the DES components and their specific interactions with the MCumS LMWG. As revealed by SEM and ATR-FTIR analysis, the zwitterionic character of betaine promotes

extensive hydrogen bonding and electrostatic interactions with the hydrophilic MCumS, resulting in a denser and more cohesive MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogel network. In contrast, the MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel incorporates Men, a less polar and more hydrophobic component, which led to a looser architecture with greater flexibility and reduced intermolecular connectivity.

Dynamic step-strain tests were performed to assess self-healing behavior. At low strain ($\gamma=1\%$), both eutectogels showed gel-like behavior ($G' > G''$). After applying a high strain ($\gamma=1000\%$), both systems experienced an inversion in G' and G'' values, indicating breakdown of the gel network ($G'' > G'$). Upon returning to low strain, MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogel (Figure 5c) rapidly regained its original G' , showing efficient self-healing and injectability. In contrast, MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel (Figure 5f) showed only partial recovery. These results highlight the superior strength and thixotropic recovery of MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogel, likely driven by stronger supramolecular interactions in its hydrogen bond-rich medium.

Figure 5. Storage modulus (G' , solid squares) and loss modulus (G'' , hollow squares) of MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogel as a function of the (a) oscillation strain at 1 Hz and (b) frequency at 1% strain. (c) Dynamic step-strain amplitude tests of MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogel. G' (solid squares) and G'' (hollow squares) of MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel as a function of the (d) oscillation strain at 1 Hz and (e) frequency at 1% strain. (f) Dynamic step-strain amplitude tests of MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel.

3. Conclusions

In summary, three new fluorescent LMWGs based on D-sorbitol were successfully synthesized through a straightforward synthetic approach. Solvent screening revealed distinct gelation behavior: DNapS preferentially gelled low-polarity solvents such as toluene and 1,4-dioxane, DBTDS formed organogels in toluene, EtOAc, and EtOH, while MCumS exhibited gelation mainly in water and longer-chain alcohols. Based on this screening, representative gel systems -DNapS/toluene, DBTDS/EtOAc, and MCumS/water- were selected for in-depth structural investigation.

Fluorescence spectroscopy confirmed the emissive behavior of these LMWGs in both solution and gel states. Multiscale characterization demonstrated that gelation in conventional solvents arises from hierarchical self-assembly driven by cooperative hydrogen bonding and π - π interactions, leading to flexible or semi-flexible supramolecular fibrils with nanometric cross-sections. SAXS, SEM, and XRD analyses revealed that variations in fibrillar organization, lamellar packing, and network compactness directly govern the resulting gel architecture, ranging from dense bundled assemblies to highly porous networks.

Among the three LMWGs, MCumS displayed an ambidextrous character, which suggested its potential for extending the studies to DES environments. Rheological analysis indicated that the MCumS/Thy:Bet eutectogel is stronger and more rigid than the MCumS/Thy:Men eutectogel. However, the latter displays greater ductility, withstanding larger strains before failure.

Overall, these D-sorbitol-derived fluorescent LMWGs combine structural adaptability, simple synthesis, and compatibility with green solvents, highlighting their potential as versatile building blocks for the development of functional supramolecular fluorescent gels and for advancing the fundamental understanding of structure-organization-property relationships in advanced soft-material.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank for technical and human support provided by SGIker (UPV/EHU/ ERDF, EU). The authors also thank CIC biomaGUNE for their valuable collaboration in the circular dichroism experiments. This work was funded by the European Union under the IONBIKE 2.0 project (grant agreement No. 101129945, <https://doi.org/10.3030/101129945>) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101034379. D. M., M. L. P., and D. M. gratefully acknowledge the financial support from IKERBASQUE-Basque Foundation for Science. M. L.

P. gratefully acknowledges the financial support from the Basque Government, Department of Education (IT1766-22). D. M. thanked Ayuda RYC2021-031668-I financed by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the European Union Next Generation EU/PRTR. E. O. also appreciates the financial support from Agencia Nacional de Promoción Científica y Tecnológica (PICT 2021/589, PICTO 2022/65). E. O. is a permanent research staff member of CONICET-Argentina.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] D. K. Smith, “Supramolecular gels – a panorama of low-molecular-weight gelators from ancient origins to next-generation technologies” *Soft Matter* **2024**, *20*, 10–70.
- [2] E. R. Draper, D. J. Adams, “Low-Molecular-Weight Gels: The State of the Art” *Chem* **2017**, *3*, 390–410.
- [3] X. Du, J. Zhou, J. Shi, B. Xu, “Supramolecular Hydrogelators and Hydrogels: From Soft Matter to Molecular Biomaterials” *Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115*, 13165–13307.
- [4] M. Criado-Gonzalez, E. Espinosa-Cano, L. Rojo, F. Boulmedais, M. R. Aguilar, R. Hernández, “Injectable Tripeptide/Polymer Nanoparticles Supramolecular Hydrogel: A Candidate for the Treatment of Inflammatory Pathologies” *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **2022**, *14*, 10068–10080.
- [5] D. K. Smith, “Supramolecular Gels as Active Tools for Reaction Engineering” *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **2025**, *64*, e202502053.
- [6] M. Criado-Gonzalez, M. I. Peñas, F. Barbault, A. J. Müller, F. Boulmedais, R. Hernández, “Salt-induced Fmoc-tripeptide supramolecular hydrogels: a combined experimental and computational study of the self-assembly” *Nanoscale* **2024**, *16*, 9887–

9898.

- [7] J. Li, F. Yin, J. Wang, H. Du, F. Xu, S. Meskers, Y. Li, S. Wijker, Y. Peng, R. Bellan, G. Vantomme, J. Song, C.-S. Liu, E. W. Meijer, “Self-Regulating Hydrogel with Reversible Optical Activity in Its Gel-to-Gel Transformation” *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2025**, *147*, 17361–17371.
- [8] B. O. Okesola, V. M. P. Vieira, D. J. Cornwell, N. K. Whitelaw, D. K. Smith, “1,3:2,4-Dibenzylidene-d-sorbitol (DBS) and its derivatives-efficient, versatile and industrially-relevant low-molecular-weight gelators with over 100 years of history and a bright future” *Soft Matter* **2015**, *11*, 4768–4787.
- [9] J. Ruiz-Olles, P. Slavik, N. K. Whitelaw, D. K. Smith, “Self-Assembled Gels Formed in Deep Eutectic Solvents: Supramolecular Eutectogels with High Ionic Conductivity” *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **2019**, *58*, 4173–4178.
- [10] W. Lai, C. Wu, “Studies on the self-assembly of neat DBS and DBS/PPG organogels” *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.* **2010**, *115*, 1113–1119.
- [11] W. C. Lai, P. H. Huang, “Self-assembly behaviors of dibenzylidene sorbitol hybrid organogels with inorganic silica” *Soft Matter* **2017**, *13*, 3107–3115.
- [12] K. K. Diehn, H. Oh, R. Hashemipour, R. G. Weiss, S. R. Raghavan, “Insights into organogelation and its kinetics from Hansen solubility parameters. Toward a priori predictions of molecular gelation” *Soft Matter* **2014**, *10*, 2632.
- [13] W.-C. Lai, S.-C. Tseng, “Novel polymeric nanocomposites and porous materials prepared using organogels” *Nanotechnology* **2009**, *20*, 475606.
- [14] R. H. C. Janssen, V. Stümpflen, M. C. W. van Boxtel, C. W. M. Bastiaansen, D. J. Broer, T. A. Tervoort, P. Smith, “Thermo-reversible gelation of liquid crystals using dibenzylidene-D-sorbitol” *Macromol. Symp.* **2000**, *154*, 117–126.
- [15] G. de Araujo Lima e Souza, M. E. Di Pietro, V. Vanoli, W. Panzeri, F. Briatico-Vangosa, F. Castiglione, A. Mele, “Hydrophobic eutectogels: a new outfit for non-ionic eutectic solvents” *Mater. Today Chem.* **2023**, *29*, 101402.
- [16] D. J. Cornwell, B. O. Okesola, D. K. Smith, “Hybrid polymer and low molecular weight gels – dynamic two-component soft materials with both responsive and robust nanoscale networks” *Soft Matter* **2013**, *9*, 8730.
- [17] B. O. Okesola, D. K. Smith, “Versatile supramolecular pH-tolerant hydrogels which

- demonstrate pH-dependent selective adsorption of dyes from aqueous solution” *Chem. Commun.* **2013**, *49*, 11164.
- [18] Y. Li, D. J. Young, X. J. Loh, “Fluorescent gels: a review of synthesis, properties, applications and challenges” *Mater. Chem. Front.* **2019**, *3*, 1489–1502.
- [19] M. Criado-Gonzalez, N. Alegret, A. M. Fracaroli, D. Mantione, G. Guzmán-González, R. Del Olmo, K. Tashiro, L. C. Tomé, M. L. Picchio, D. Mecerreyes, “Mixed Conductive, Injectable, and Fluorescent Supramolecular Eutectogel Composites” *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* **2023**, *62*, e202301489.
- [20] X. Cao, A. Gao, J. Hou, T. Yi, “Fluorescent supramolecular self-assembly gels and their application as sensors: A review” *Coord. Chem. Rev.* **2021**, *434*, 213792.
- [21] Q. Han, Q. Wang, A. Gao, X.-P. Chang, L. Zeng, X. Cao, “Robust Fluorescent Self-Assembly System for Sensing of Phosgene, Thionyl Chloride, and Oxalyl Chloride” *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2023**, *11*, 2139–2150.
- [22] S. S. Babu, V. K. Praveen, A. Ajayaghosh, “Functional π -Gelators and Their Applications” *Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *114*, 1973–2129.
- [23] G. Wang, S. B. Adhikari, P. Aryal, I. Okafor, A. Chen, A. Duffney, “Synthesis and Characterization of Coumarin Containing Fluorescent Sugar Based Gelators” *Carbohydr. Res.* **2025**, 109526.
- [24] V. Singh, K. Lalitha, C. U. Maheswari, V. Sridharan, D. Pradhan, S. Batra, S. Nagarajan, “Remediation of Dyes Using Supramolecular Material Derived from Carbohydrate Based π -Gelator Using the Bottom-Up Assembly Approach” *ACS Omega* **2024**, *9*, 5695–5704.
- [25] M. Watase, Y. Nakatani, H. Itagaki, “On the Origin of the Formation and Stability of Physical Gels of Di- O -benzylidene- d -sorbitol” *J. Phys. Chem. B* **1999**, *103*, 2366–2373.
- [26] J. Li, K. Fan, L. Niu, Y. Li, J. Song, “Effects of Salt on the Gelation Mechanism of a D-Sorbitol-Based Hydrogelator” *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2013**, *117*, 5989–5995.
- [27] K. Fan, J. Song, J. Li, X. Guan, N. Tao, C. Tong, H. Shen, L. Niu, “Copper(ii)-responsive gel–sol phase transition in supramolecular gel systems of salen-appended sorbitol” *J. Mater. Chem. C* **2013**, *1*, 7479.
- [28] H. Wang, W. Zhang, X. Dong, Y. Yang, “Thermo-reversibility of the fluorescence

- enhancement of acridine orange induced by supramolecular self-assembly” *Talanta* **2009**, *77*, 1864–1868.
- [29] F. Wen, J. Li, L. Wang, F. Li, H. Yu, B. Li, K. Fan, X. Guan, “Novel self-healing and multi-stimuli-responsive supramolecular gel based on D-sorbitol diacetal for multifunctional applications” *RSC Adv.* **2021**, *11*, 32459–32463.
- [30] P. A. Mercadal, A. González, A. Beloqui, L. C. Tomé, D. Mecerreyes, M. Calderón, M. L. Picchio, “Eutectogels: The Multifaceted Soft Ionic Materials of Tomorrow” *JACS Au* **2024**, *4*, 3744–3758.
- [31] J. L. de Lacalle, M. L. Picchio, A. Dominguez-Alfaro, R. R.-M. Serrano, B. Marchiori, I. del Agua, N. Lopez-Larrea, M. Criado-Gonzalez, G. G. Malliaras, D. Mecerreyes, “Hydrophobic Eutectogels as Electrodes for Underwater Electromyography Recording” *ACS Mater. Lett.* **2023**, *5*, 3340–3346.
- [32] J. M. Gardlik, R. V. Burkes, *Process for Preparing Dibenzylidene-D-Sorbitol Compounds*, **1992**.
- [33] G. C. Dizon, G. Atkinson, S. P. Argent, L. T. Santu, D. B. Amabilino, “Sustainable sorbitol-derived compounds for gelation of the full range of ethanol–water mixtures” *Soft Matter* **2020**, *16*, 4640–4654.
- [34] P. Li, S. Ma, B. Wang, X. Xu, H. Feng, Z. Yu, T. Yu, Y. Liu, J. Zhu, “Degradable benzyl cyclic acetal epoxy monomers with low viscosity: Synthesis, structure-property relationships, application in recyclable carbon fiber composite” *Compos. Sci. Technol.* **2022**, *219*, 109243.
- [35] I. Rozas, I. Alkorta, J. Elguero, “Bifurcated Hydrogen Bonds: Three-Centered Interactions” *J. Phys. Chem. A* **1998**, *102*, 9925–9932.
- [36] R. A. Nyquist, S. E. Settineri, “Infrared Study of Coumarin in Different Solvent Systems” *Appl. Spectrosc.* **1990**, *44*, 791–796.
- [37] C. N. R. Rao, R. Venkataraghavan, T. R. Kasturi, “Contribution to the Infrared Spectra of Organosulphur Compounds” *Can. J. Chem.* **1964**, *42*, 36–42.
- [38] N. Yan, G. He, H. Zhang, L. Ding, Y. Fang, “Glucose-Based Fluorescent Low-Molecular Mass Compounds: Creation of Simple and Versatile Supramolecular Gelators” *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 5909–5917.
- [39] Z. Yang, G. Liang, M. Ma, Y. Gao, B. Xu, “Conjugates of naphthalene and dipeptides

- produce molecular hydrogelators with high efficiency of hydrogelation and superhelical nanofibers” *J. Mater. Chem.* **2007**, *17*, 850–854.
- [40] L. Chen, S. Revel, K. Morris, L. C. Serpell, D. J. Adams, “Effect of Molecular Structure on the Properties of Naphthalene–Dipeptide Hydrogelators” *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 13466–13471.
- [41] H. Vilaça, A. Carvalho, T. Castro, E. M. S. Castanheira, L. Hilliou, I. Hamley, M. Melle-Franco, P. M. T. Ferreira, J. A. Martins, “Unveiling the Role of Capping Groups in Naphthalene N-Capped Dehydrodipeptide Hydrogels” *Gels* **2023**, *9*, 464.
- [42] E. R. Draper, B. Dietrich, K. McAulay, C. Brasnett, H. Abdizadeh, I. Patmanidis, S. J. Marrink, H. Su, H. Cui, R. Schweins, A. Seddon, D. J. Adams, “Using Small-Angle Scattering and Contrast Matching to Understand Molecular Packing in Low Molecular Weight Gels” *Matter* **2020**, *2*, 764–778.
- [43] D. McDowall, D. J. Adams, A. M. Seddon, “Using small angle scattering to understand low molecular weight gels” *Soft Matter* **2022**, *18*, 1577–1590.
- [44] L. L. E. Mears, E. R. Draper, A. M. Castilla, H. Su, Zhuola, B. Dietrich, M. C. Nolan, G. N. Smith, J. Douth, S. Rogers, R. Akhtar, H. Cui, D. J. Adams, “Drying Affects the Fiber Network in Low Molecular Weight Hydrogels” *Biomacromolecules* **2017**, *18*, 3531–3540.
- [45] A. Z. Cardoso, L. L. E. Mears, B. N. Cattoz, P. C. Griffiths, R. Schweins, D. J. Adams, “Linking micellar structures to hydrogelation for salt-triggered dipeptide gelators” *Soft Matter* **2016**, *12*, 3612–3621.
- [46] E. R. Draper, M. Wallace, R. Schweins, R. J. Poole, D. J. Adams, “Nonlinear Effects in Multicomponent Supramolecular Hydrogels” *Langmuir* **2017**, *33*, 2387–2395.
- [47] A. M. Castilla, E. R. Draper, M. C. Nolan, C. Brasnett, A. Seddon, L. L. E. Mears, N. Cowieson, D. J. Adams, “Self-sorted Oligophenylvinylene and Perylene Bisimide Hydrogels” *Sci. Rep.* **2017**, *7*, 8380.
- [48] C. R. M. MacDonald, E. R. Draper, “Applications of microscopy and small angle scattering techniques for the characterisation of supramolecular gels” *Beilstein J. Org. Chem.* **2024**, *20*, 2608–2634.
- [49] J. Song, H. Sun, S. Sun, R. Feng, “Synthesis and gel properties of sorbitol derivative gelators” *Trans. Tianjin Univ.* **2013**, *19*, 319–325.

- [50] A. Paiva, R. Craveiro, I. Aroso, M. Martins, R. L. Reis, A. R. C. Duarte, “Natural Deep Eutectic Solvents – Solvents for the 21st Century” *ACS Sustain. Chem. Eng.* **2014**, *2*, 1063–1071.
- [51] C. Zeng, H. Zhao, Z. Wan, Q. Xiao, H. Xia, S. Guo, “Highly biodegradable, thermostable eutectogels prepared by gelation of natural deep eutectic solvents using xanthan gum: preparation and characterization” *RSC Adv.* **2020**, *10*, 28376–28382.
- [52] M. L. Picchio, M. S. Orellano, M. A. Motta, C. Huck-Iriart, D. Sánchez-deAlcázar, R. López-Domene, B. Martín-García, A. Larrañaga, A. Beloqui, D. Mecerreyes, M. Calderón, “Elastomeric Protein Bioactive Eutectogels for Topical Drug Delivery” *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2024**, *34*, 1–10.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Table of Contents

Sugar-based fluorescent low-molecular-weight gelators (LMWGs) DNapS, DBTDS, and MCumS, prepared by a green scalable route, form supramolecular gels in water, organic and deep eutectic solvents. MCumS yields solvent-dependent nanofibrous networks and viscoelastic injectable eutectogels.